

Harmonic Unbiased Estimator: Some Properties

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Abstract – In an earlier study, concept of harmonic unbiased estimator was introduced and defined based on harmonic expectation. Attempt has here been made to identify some important properties/facts/results of harmonic unbiased estimator. This article is based on the information on this unbiased estimator obtained in the attempt.

Keywords: Estimation, Harmonic Unbiasedness, HUE, Some Properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

Unbiasedness, in the literature of statistical estimation, is regarded as a desirable property/quality/criterion of an estimator [1, 8, 12, 13]. Originally, the concept of unbiasedness [8, 9] was explained on the basis of the mathematical expectation [2, 11, 14], more specifically the arithmetic expectation, of the estimator concerned and accordingly unbiased estimator was defined [1, 12, 13]. This definition later was termed as arithmetic unbiased estimator [6]. Recently, concepts of harmonic unbiased estimator [6] was introduced and defined based on harmonic expectation [3, 4, 5, 7]. Attempt has here been made on identifying some important properties/facts/results of harmonic unbiased estimator. This article is based on the information on this unbiased estimator obtained in the attempt.

2. HARMONIC UNBIASED ESTIMATOR

Suppose,

$$X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n$$

is a random sample drawn from a population of a non-zero real valued random variable X which follows a probability distribution having parameter θ

$$\& \quad T = T(X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n)$$

is an estimator of θ .

Then T can be regarded as harmonic unbiased estimator of parameter θ if

$$E_H(T) = \theta$$

where $E_H(T)$ is the harmonic expectation of T .

Let us abbreviate harmonic unbiased estimator by HUE.

Note:

HUE exists in the case of non-zero real valued estimator. The corresponding parameter θ , in this case, is an unknown non-zero real number.

3. ALGEBRAIC PROPERTIES OF HARMONIC UNBIASED IN ESTIMATOR

Property (1): If T is HUE of parameter θ then $c.T$ is HUE of parameter $c.\theta$.

Proof: This follows from the fact that

$$E_H(c.T) = c.E_H(T) = c.\theta$$

Corollary: If T is HUE of parameter θ then $-T$ is HUE of parameter $-\theta$.

This follows from the fact that

$$E_H(-T) = -E_H(T) = -\theta$$

Property (2): Harmonic mean (HM) of a finite number of HUEs of a parameter θ is also HUE of the parameter θ .

Proof: Suppose, T and S are two HUEs of a parameter θ .

Then

$$\begin{aligned} E_H(\text{HM of } T \text{ and } S) &= E_H\left(\frac{2}{\frac{1}{T} + \frac{1}{S}}\right) \\ &= 2E_H\left\{\left(\frac{1}{T} + \frac{1}{S}\right)^{-1}\right\} \\ &= 2\left\{EA\left(\frac{1}{T} + \frac{1}{S}\right)\right\}^{-1}, \text{ (where } EA(T) \text{ is the arithmetic expectation of } T) \\ &= 2\left\{EA\left(\frac{1}{T}\right) + EA\left(\frac{1}{S}\right)\right\}^{-1} \\ &= 2\left[\left\{E_H(T)\right\}^{-1} + \left\{E_H(S)\right\}^{-1}\right]^{-1} \\ &= 2(\theta^{-1} + \theta^{-1})^{-1} \\ &= \theta \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, HM of T and S is HUE of a parameter θ .

Now suppose,

$$T_1, T_2, \dots, T_r$$

are r HUEs of a parameter θ .

Then

$$\text{HM of } T_1, T_2, \dots, T_r = \frac{r}{\frac{1}{T_1} + \frac{1}{T_2} + \dots + \frac{1}{T_r}}$$

Proceeding similarly as in the earlier case, one can obtain that

$$E_H\left(\frac{r}{\frac{1}{T_1} + \frac{1}{T_2} + \dots + \frac{1}{T_r}}\right) = \theta$$

Therefore, HM of T_1, T_2, \dots, T_r is HUE of θ .

Thus, Property (2) has been proved for a finite number of estimators.

Hence, Property (2) has been established.

Property (3): There may exists more than one HUE of a parameter.

Proof: Let us consider a population following the uniform discrete distribution [10] described by the probability mass function

$$P(X = X_i) = \frac{1}{K} , (X_i = 1, 2, \dots, K)$$

with population harmonic mean μ_H where

$$\mu_H = \left(\frac{1}{\frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K \frac{1}{K}} \right)$$

Suppose,

$$X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n$$

is a random sample drawn from this population.

Then each element of the sample assumes the values

1, 2, \dots, k

with equal probability $\frac{1}{K}$,

so that by the definition of harmonic expectation,

$$E_H(X_i) = \left(\frac{1}{\frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^K \frac{1}{K}} \right) = \mu_H , \text{ for each } X_i \text{ (} i = 1, 2, \dots, k \text{)}$$

This implies each X_i is a HUE of μ_H .

By Property (3),

HM of any two elements of the sample is HUE of μ_H .

Similarly, HM of any three elements of the sample is also HUE of μ_H ,

HM of any four elements of the sample is also HUE of μ_H

and so on.

Thus, Property (3) has been established.

Property (4): There may not exists HUE of a parameter.

Proof: Let us consider a population following binomial distribution [10] having parameters R (number of trials) and p (probability of success).

Suppose

$$X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n$$

is a random sample drawn from this population.

For this distribution, HUE of the binomial parameter p does not exist.

Thus, Property (4) has been established.

Property (5): If T is HUE of parameter θ and S is HUE of parameter φ then HM of T and S is HUE of the HM of θ and φ .

In general, if

$$T_1, T_2, \dots, T_r$$

are r HUEs of the respective parameters

$$\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_r,$$

then the HM of T_1, T_2, \dots, T_r , is HUE of the HM of $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_r$.

Proof: This follows from the fact that We

$$\begin{aligned} E_H(\text{HM of T and S}) &= E_H\left(\frac{2}{\frac{1}{T} + \frac{1}{S}}\right) \\ &= 2E_H\left\{\left(\frac{1}{T} + \frac{1}{S}\right)^{-1}\right\} \\ &= 2\left\{E_A\left(\frac{1}{T} + \frac{1}{S}\right)\right\}^{-1}, \text{ (where } E_A(T) \text{ is the arithmetic expectation of T)} \\ &= 2\left\{E_A\left(\frac{1}{T}\right) + E_A\left(\frac{1}{S}\right)\right\}^{-1} \\ &= 2\left[\left\{E_H(T)\right\}^{-1} + \left\{E_H(S)\right\}^{-1}\right]^{-1} \\ &= 2(\theta^{-1} + \varphi^{-1})^{-1} \\ &= \text{HM HM of } \theta \text{ and } \varphi \end{aligned}$$

Proceeding similarly as in the earlier case, one can obtain that

$$E_H(\text{HM of } T_1, T_2, \dots, T_r) = \text{HM of } \theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_r$$

Hence, Property (5) has been established.

4. CONCLUSION

Concept of geometric unbiasedness is likely to be useful and/or helpful in finding unbiased estimator of a parameter in the situation where the associated data are of ratio type or other allied types.

The properties of geometric unbiased estimator, obtained here, are likely to be useful and/or helpful in finding unbiased estimator of a function of parameter in the similar situations.

Moreover, the properties of geometric unbiased estimator are likely to be important and useful in enriching the theory of statistical estimation.

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